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PROPERTIES OF POROUS YTTRIA STABILIZED ZIRCONIA IMPREGRATING WITH SILICA AEROGELS

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Introduction

Low thermal conductivity-YSZ

Porous YSZ

- **Advantage**
 - High strength
 - Easy forming
- **Disadvantage**
 - High thermal conductivity

Introduction

Silica aerogels have been examined for numerous applications owing to their low density, high porosity, and thermal insulating properties.

Bulk density (g/cm^3)	0.1~0.3
Porosity (%)	80~99.8
Mean pore size (nm)	~10
Thermal conductivity ($\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$) (Air, 300K)	0.017~0.03

Introduction

silica aerogel insulating tile

Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. 1998, 37, 22

Aerogel applications over large areas in new buildings

Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews
34(2014) 288

(a)

(b)

(c)

ASPEN Co. production (a)shoes,(b)cold resistance clothes,(c)pipeline

Aerogels

- Advantage

low thermal conductivity

- Disadvantage

Low strength

Difficult to form

Objective

Experimental-Preparation method

gel-casting method

Preparing slurry deairing
Molding
Gelation
drying and sintering.

+

sol

immersed by application of
vacuum

Hydrolysis
Condensation
Gelation
supercritical drying process

Results & discussion

porous YSZ matrix

silica aerogels

Results & discussion

porous YSZ after impregnation

Results & discussion

Results & discussion

Conclusions

- Impregnation with silica aerogels in the pores of the porous YSZ ceramics was obviously observed.
- Silica aerogel occupied most of the pore volume, resulting in a significant decrease in porosity.
- It is found that the thermal conductivity was lowered and the compressive strength was increased after impregnating of silica aerogels.

Thank you for your attention.